

Mankanai Inscription* of Gajabhahu II

THIS inscription was discovered in the village of Mānkanai in the Trincomalee district about eight miles north of Trincomalee town. The slab on which the inscription is written is now kept in the Archaeological Museum at Anuradhapura.

The record is in two parts. The first part is in fairly good condition; but in the second part certain lines and letters are damaged. Each part of the inscription contains 22 lines of writing incised between parallel lines. The second part ends with the following sign:

The script is Tamil with a few Grantha letters. The proper names of kings such as Sri Jayabhāhu, Gajabhāhu, are written in Grantha. But the name Māñāparaṇa is written in Tamil characters.

The language is Tamil. But it contains some words of Sinhalese origin such as *Tel Vecār*, *Kiratu*, *Narātu vecār*, *Veyaka* and *Verattāna*. The word *Tel Vecār* is probably from Sinh. *Tel vāsara*. It means "the agricultural land named *Tel*".¹ The word *Veyaka* may be derived from Sinh. word *vē*, *vehe* = Skt. *vīthi* or *vīthī*, Pkt. *vihī*, *vihīya*.² The Sanskrit word *āgñā* changes into *āññai* in Tamil. This is used in the sense of *ānai* 'vow'. *Verattāna* is from the Skt. words *vihāra* and *sthāna*. The Sanskrit word *vigna* has become *vikka* by the assimilation of *gn* into *gg** > *kk*. The Tamil past adverbial participle *kuṭuttu* from the $\sqrt{\text{kuṭu}}$ — is used as a finite verb. The word *cūḷuravu* is used in the sense of 'oath'.³ The writing and the style are the same as the ones found in the South Indian Tamil records of the eleventh and twelfth centuries. No puḷḷi is used to indicate the consonants in the inscription.

The inscription is issued by Gajabhāhu (A.D. 1131-1153), but it is dated in the 43rd regnal year of his predecessor Jayabhāhu (A.D. 1108-1145/6). This way of dating records from the date of the coronation of a dead king

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1. See discussion on the word *Veva-sara* by S. Paranavitana in EZ, Vol. IV, pp. 124, 125.
2. See Wickramasinghe, EZ, Vol. I, pp. 51 f.n. 13.
3. See Iṟaiyaṇār Kaḷaviyal Urai Cūt. 18.

Mankanai Inscription of Gajabhāhu II

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is known from other epigraphs.⁴ Though the record was given by Gajabhāhu, it is known from the second part of the inscription that it was inscribed on stone by Mānāparaṇa alias Virabhāhu 1196 A.D. who was ruling in the Southern Country.⁵

The object of the record is to register the donation for life of certain paddy lands to one *Mintan Korran*, the overseer of the palanquin bearers of the palace.

I

<i>Text</i>	<i>Transliteration</i>
1. ஸ்வஸ்தி ஸ்ரீ அ	1. Svasti sri a
2. பைய சலாமெ	2. paiya calāme
3. கபநமரான ச	3. ka panmarāna ca
4. ககரவாததிக	4. kkaravarttika
5. ஸ்ரீ ஜயவா ஹ	5. ś sri Jayabhāhu
6. தெவறககு யாண	6. tevaṛkku yāṇ
7. சையந ஆவது தி	7. ṭu 43 āvatu ti
8. ருப்பளளி ச சிவின	8. ruppallie civi
9. கயாரில கணகா	9. kaiyāril kaṅkā
10. ணி மிந்தன கொ	10. ṇi Mintan Ko
11. றிறநென மஜவா	11. ṛranen Gajabhā
12. ஹ தெவா எநககுஜி	12. hu tevar enakkuji
13. விதமாக இ (ட) ட இ	13. vitamāka i(t)ṭa i
14. த தெல வெசாரும்	14. t telvecārum
15. கிரது நராது வெ	15. kiratu narātu ve
16. சாரும் இதில நாற	16. cārum itil nāṛ
17. பால எலலை பெரு	17. pāl ellai peru
18. மாள மஜவா	18. māḷ Gajabhā
19. ஹ தெவா வெய	19. hu tevar veyā
20. க வெரத்தான பரி	20. ka verattāna pari
21. ததலகுமிதானம	21. tta bhūmi tāṇam
22. ாக இட்டருளிந.	22. āka iṭṭaruḷina.

4. See S. Paranavitana, EZ, Vol. II, pp. 200-202.

5. See H. W. Codrington: A Short History of Ceylon, p. 13 and p. 58. The term "Southern Country" according to him began in the south of the present North Central Province, developed into Māyāraṇa. In the 12th century it extended over the western part of Matale, the whole of North Western Province and the greater part of the Western and Sabaragamuwa Provinces. At the time of this inscription it went probably as far as certain parts of Trincomalee district. In the Paṇḍuvasnuvara inscription of Kurunegala district it is referred to as தென்னிலங்கை. (South Ceylon).

II

<i>Text</i>	<i>Transliteration</i>
1. நிருபதி (த)	1. nirupati (ta)
2. (ந) குறிப்பு	2. n kurippu
3. ககு மாண	3. kku Māṇā
4. பரண தெ	4. paraṇa te
5. வர மஜவ	5. var Gajabh
6. ா ஹதெவா	6. āhu tevar
7. செயதது செ	7. ceytatu ce
8. ய லென்று	8. yalenru
9. அருளி திருமு	9. aruḷi tirumu
10. கம வரக்கா	10. kam varakkā
11. டடிச சிலா	11. ṭṭic cilā
12. லெகம செ	12. lekam ce
13. யது குடு	13. ytu kuṭu
14. தது த்து	14. ttu ittu
15. ககு ஒருவி	15. kku oruvi
16. கககு செ(ய)	16. kkañ ce(ya)
17. (லென்று) ளம	17. (lenru) ḷama
18. திப புத்தரா	18. tip puttara
19. குளை வ	19. ṅṅai Va
20. லவவ (ரை)	20. llava (rai)
21. யன குளு	21. yaṇ cūlu
22. றவு.	22. raṇu

Translation

I

Hail! In the 43rd year of Abhayasālā Megha Varman, the Emperor Sri Jayabhāhu Deva, the agricultural land named Tel, Kiratu and the agricultural land named Narātu were given to me Mintan Korraṇ, the overseer of the palanquin bearers of the Royal Bed-Chamber, by Gajabhāhu Deva for life. The four boundaries surrounding these (the agricultural lands) are the lands belonging to the vihāra of Gajabhāhu Deva which is situated on the main road. These (the agricultural lands) are given as donation to me.

II

To this notification issued by the king, Mānābharaṇa Deva ordered "May the wishes of the king Gajabhāhu Deva be accomplished" and sent a royal letter to inscribe this (donation) on stone, ordering that no impediment should be done to this wish. This vow is taken in the name of the enlightened Buddha. This is the oath taken by Vallavarayaṇ.

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